

Theory of Phenomenological Dark Matter

Preface :

Generic Arc Length Difference :

$$\theta r = \gamma x - \alpha y \tag{1}$$

0.0.1. $\theta r = s$

0.0.2. $\gamma x = q$

0.0.3. $\alpha y = p$

0.0.4. $l\alpha = w$

$$\text{In[*]} := y^2 = l^2 - h^2 \tag{2}$$

$$\theta r = \gamma x - \alpha \sqrt{l^2 - h^2} \tag{3}$$

$$s = q - \alpha \sqrt{l^2 - h^2} \tag{4}$$

$$l \sin[\beta] = h$$

$$\text{SOH; } h/l = \sin[\beta]$$

$$\text{CAH; } y/l = \cos[\beta]$$

$$\text{TOA; } h/y = \tan[\beta]$$

$$y = \frac{q - s}{\alpha} \tag{5}$$

$$\text{In[*]} := \text{Solve}[s = q - \alpha \sqrt{l^2 - h^2}, h]$$

$$\text{Out[*]} := \left\{ \left\{ h \rightarrow -\frac{\sqrt{-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + l^2 \alpha^2}}{\alpha} \right\}, \left\{ h \rightarrow \frac{\sqrt{-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + l^2 \alpha^2}}{\alpha} \right\} \right\}$$

- h can be interpreted as acceleration, but for the purposes of this paper and algebraic architecture, it is distance .

$$\text{In[*]} := \text{Solve} \left[\frac{\sqrt{(-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + l^2 \alpha^2)} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{\alpha} = \frac{\sqrt{-(q - s - l\alpha)} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \sqrt{(q - s + l\alpha)}}{\alpha}, v \right]$$

$$\text{Out[*]} := \{\{\}\}$$

$$\text{In[*]:= Solve}\left[\frac{\sqrt{(-q^2 + 2 q s - s^2 + l^2 \alpha^2)} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{\alpha} = \frac{\sqrt{-(q - s - l \alpha)} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \sqrt{(q - s + l \alpha)}}{\alpha}, \text{Reals}\right]$$

... **Solve:** The solution set contains a full-dimensional component; use Reduce for complete solution information.

Out[*]= {{}}

$$\text{In[*]:= Solve}\left[l \text{Sin}[\beta] = \frac{\sqrt{(l \alpha + x \gamma - r \theta)} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \sqrt{(l \alpha - x \gamma + r \theta)}}{\alpha}, v\right]$$

Out[*]= {{v →

$$-\left(\left(1. \sqrt{(-8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)}\right) / \left(\sqrt{-1. l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}\right)\right)\},$$

$$\left\{v \rightarrow \left(\sqrt{(-8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)}\right) / \left(\sqrt{-1. l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}\right)\right\}$$

$$v = \frac{\sqrt{-c^2 l^2 \alpha^2 + c^2 x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 c^2 r x \gamma \theta + c^2 r^2 \theta^2 + c^2 l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}} =$$

phenomenological velocity

(6)

Cosmological Constant

Phenomenological Accleration =

$$D\left[D\left[D\left[\frac{\sqrt{-c^2 w^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 s q + c^2 s^2 + c^2 w^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. w^2 + q^2 - 2. s q + s^2 + w^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}, w\right], s\right], q\right], \beta$$

$$\text{Out[11]= } -\left(\left(1.68517 \times 10^{17} (1.79751 \times 10^{17} q - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} q + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) w^2 \text{Cos}[\beta] \text{Sin}[\beta] (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} w + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} w \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)\right) / \left(\sqrt{q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} (8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^{7/2}\right)\right) - \left(3.37033 \times 10^{16} (1.79751 \times 10^{17} q - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} q + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) w^2 \text{Cos}[\beta] \text{Sin}[\beta] (-2. w + 2 w \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)\right) / \left((q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^{3/2} (8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s +$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left. \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{5/2} \right) - \\
& \left(3.37033 \times 10^{16} (1.79751 \times 10^{17} q - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) (-2. q + 2 s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \right. \\
& \quad \left. \sin[\beta] (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} w + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} (8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \right) - \\
& \left(3 (1.79751 \times 10^{17} q - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} q + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) \right. \\
& \quad \left. w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} w + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left(8 (q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} (8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \right) - \\
& \left(3.37033 \times 10^{16} (2 q - 2. s) (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} q + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \right. \\
& \quad \left. \sin[\beta] (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} w + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} (8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \right) + \\
& \left(1.34813 \times 10^{17} (1.79751 \times 10^{17} q - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} q + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) \right. \\
& \quad \left. w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right) / \\
& \left(\sqrt{q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2} (8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \right) - \\
& \left(1.21164 \times 10^{34} w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} w + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left(\sqrt{q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2} (8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \right) - \\
& \left(3.37033 \times 10^{16} (1.79751 \times 10^{17} q - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) (-2. q + 2 s) w^2 \right. \\
& \quad \left. \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2. w + 2 w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} (8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} \right) - \\
& \left(3 (1.79751 \times 10^{17} q - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} q + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) \right. \\
& \quad \left. w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2. w + 2 w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left(8 (q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} (8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} \right) - \\
& \left(3.37033 \times 10^{16} (2 q - 2. s) (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} q + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) w^2 \right. \\
& \quad \left. \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2. w + 2 w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} (8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} \right) - \\
& \left(3 (1.79751 \times 10^{17} q - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) (-2. q + 2 s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(-1.79751 \times 10^{17} w + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} w \sin[\beta]^2 \right) / \\
& \left(8 \left(q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{5/2} \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{3/2} \right) - \\
& \left(3.37033 \times 10^{16} (2 q - 2. s) (-2. q + 2 s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left(-1.79751 \times 10^{17} w + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} w \sin[\beta]^2 \right) \right) / \\
& \left(\left(q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{5/2} \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{3/2} \right) - \\
& \left(3 (2 q - 2. s) (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} q + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left(-1.79751 \times 10^{17} w + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} w \sin[\beta]^2 \right) \right) / \\
& \left(8 \left(q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{5/2} \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{3/2} \right) + \\
& \left(4.49378 \times 10^{16} (1.79751 \times 10^{17} q - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) (-2. q + 2 s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right) / \\
& \left(\left(q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{3/2} \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{3/2} \right) + \\
& \left((1.79751 \times 10^{17} q - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} q + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) \right. \\
& \quad \left. w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right) / \\
& \left(2 \left(q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{3/2} \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{3/2} \right) + \\
& \left(4.49378 \times 10^{16} (2 q - 2. s) (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} q + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right) / \\
& \left(\left(q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{3/2} \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{3/2} \right) - \\
& \left(4.0388 \times 10^{33} w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2. w + 2 w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left(\left(q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{3/2} \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{3/2} \right) - \\
& \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} w + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left(\left(q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{3/2} \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{3/2} \right) + \\
& \left(1.61552 \times 10^{34} w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right) / \left(\sqrt{q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2} \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{3/2} \right) - \\
& \left(15 (1.79751 \times 10^{17} q - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) (-2. q + 2 s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right. \\
& \quad \left. (-2. w + 2 w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left(8 \left(q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^{7/2} \sqrt{\left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + \right.} \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left. \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right) \right) - \\
& \left(1.68517 \times 10^{17} (2q - 2s) (-2q + 2s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2w + 2w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2qs + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{7/2} \sqrt{(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} qs + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2) \right) - \\
& \left(15 (2q - 2s) (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} q + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \right. \\
& \quad \left. \sin[\beta] (-2w + 2w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left(8 (q^2 - 2qs + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{7/2} \sqrt{(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} qs + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2) \right) - \left(15 (2q - 2s) \right. \\
& \quad \left. (-2q + 2s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} w + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left(8 (q^2 - 2qs + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{7/2} \sqrt{(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} qs + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2) \right) + \\
& \left(3 (1.79751 \times 10^{17} q - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) (-2q + 2s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right) / \\
& \left(2 (q^2 - 2qs + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \sqrt{(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} qs + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2) \right) + \\
& \left(1.34813 \times 10^{17} (2q - 2s) (-2q + 2s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2qs + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \sqrt{(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} qs + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2) \right) + \\
& \left(3 (2q - 2s) (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} q + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right) / \\
& \left(2 (q^2 - 2qs + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \sqrt{(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} qs + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2) \right) - \\
& \left(2.69627 \times 10^{17} w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2w + 2w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2qs + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \sqrt{(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} qs + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2) \right) - \\
& \left(1.5 w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-1.79751 \times 10^{17} w + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2qs + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \sqrt{(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} qs + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2) \right) + \\
& \left(3.59502 \times 10^{17} w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right) / \left((q^2 - 2qs + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} \right. \\
& \quad \left. \sqrt{(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} qs + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2) \right) + \\
& \left(105 (2q - 2s) (-2q + 2s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2w + 2w \sin[\beta]^2) \right. \\
& \quad \left. \sqrt{(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} qs + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \left(8 (q^2 - 2qs + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{9/2} \right) -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(15 (2 q - 2. s) (-2. q + 2 s) w \text{Cos}[\beta] \text{Sin}[\beta] \sqrt{(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} \right) / \\
& \left(2 (q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^{7/2} \right) + \left(7.5 w^2 \text{Cos}[\beta] \text{Sin}[\beta] (-2. w + 2 w \text{Sin}[\beta]^2) \right. \\
& \left. \sqrt{(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} \right) / (q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^{7/2} - \\
& \left(6. w \text{Cos}[\beta] \text{Sin}[\beta] \sqrt{(8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} w^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} \right) / (q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 - 1. w^2 + w^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^{5/2}
\end{aligned}$$

```

In[12]:= Manipulate[SphericalPlot3D[
- ((1.685165960131533`*^17 (1.7975103574736352`*^17 q - 1.7975103574736352`*^17 s)
(-1.7975103574736352`*^17 q + 1.7975103574736352`*^17 s) w^2 Cos[\beta] Sin[\beta]
(-1.7975103574736352`*^17 w + 1.7975103574736352`*^17 w Sin[\beta]^2)) /
(\sqrt{q^2 - 2.` q s + s^2 - 1.` w^2 + w^2 Sin[\beta]^2} (8.987551787368176`*^16 q^2 -
1.7975103574736352`*^17 q s + 8.987551787368176`*^16 s^2 -
8.987551787368176`*^16 w^2 + 8.987551787368176`*^16 w^2 Sin[\beta]^2)^{7/2}) -
(3.370331920263066`*^16 (1.7975103574736352`*^17 q - 1.7975103574736352`*^17 s)
(-1.7975103574736352`*^17 q + 1.7975103574736352`*^17 s)
w^2 Cos[\beta] Sin[\beta] (-2.` w + 2 w Sin[\beta]^2)) /
((q^2 - 2.` q s + s^2 - 1.` w^2 + w^2 Sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} (8.987551787368176`*^16 q^2 -
1.7975103574736352`*^17 q s + 8.987551787368176`*^16 s^2 -
8.987551787368176`*^16 w^2 + 8.987551787368176`*^16 w^2 Sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2}) -
(3.370331920263066`*^16 (1.7975103574736352`*^17 q - 1.7975103574736352`*^17 s)
(-2.` q + 2 s) w^2 Cos[\beta] Sin[\beta]
(-1.7975103574736352`*^17 w + 1.7975103574736352`*^17 w Sin[\beta]^2)) /
((q^2 - 2.` q s + s^2 - 1.` w^2 + w^2 Sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} (8.987551787368176`*^16 q^2 -
1.7975103574736352`*^17 q s + 8.987551787368176`*^16 s^2 -
8.987551787368176`*^16 w^2 + 8.987551787368176`*^16 w^2 Sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2}) -
(3 (1.7975103574736352`*^17 q - 1.7975103574736352`*^17 s)
(-1.7975103574736352`*^17 q + 1.7975103574736352`*^17 s) w^2 Cos[\beta] Sin[\beta]
(-1.7975103574736352`*^17 w + 1.7975103574736352`*^17 w Sin[\beta]^2)) /
(8 (q^2 - 2.` q s + s^2 - 1.` w^2 + w^2 Sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} (8.987551787368176`*^16 q^2 -
1.7975103574736352`*^17 q s + 8.987551787368176`*^16 s^2 -
8.987551787368176`*^16 w^2 + 8.987551787368176`*^16 w^2 Sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2}) -
(3.370331920263066`*^16 (2 q - 2.` s) (-1.7975103574736352`*^17 q +
1.7975103574736352`*^17 s) w^2 Cos[\beta] Sin[\beta]

```

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(-1.7975103574736352 \cdot w + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot w \sin[\beta]^2 \right) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \right) + \\
& (1.3481327681052264 \cdot (1.7975103574736352 \cdot q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) \\
& \quad (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot q + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta]) / \\
& \left(\sqrt{q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \right) - \\
& (1.2116413069593733 \cdot w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot w + \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot w \sin[\beta]^2)) / \\
& \left(\sqrt{q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \right) - \\
& (3.370331920263066 \cdot (1.7975103574736352 \cdot q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) \\
& \quad (-2 \cdot q + 2 s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2 w \sin[\beta]^2)) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} \right) - \\
& (3 (1.7975103574736352 \cdot q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) \\
& \quad (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot q + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) \\
& \quad w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2 w \sin[\beta]^2)) / \\
& \left(8 (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} \right) - \\
& (3.370331920263066 \cdot (2 q - 2 \cdot s) (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot q + \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2 w \sin[\beta]^2)) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} \right) - \\
& (3 (1.7975103574736352 \cdot q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) (-2 \cdot q + 2 s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \\
& \quad \sin[\beta] (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot w + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot w \sin[\beta]^2)) / \\
& \left(8 (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} - \\
& (3.370331920263066 \cdot 10^{16} (2q - 2 \cdot s) (-2 \cdot q + 2s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \\
& (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w \sin^2[\beta])) / \\
& ((q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{5/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2}) - \\
& (3 (2q - 2 \cdot s) (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \\
& \sin[\beta] (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w \sin^2[\beta])) / \\
& (8 (q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{5/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2}) + \\
& (4.493775893684088 \cdot 10^{16} (1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) \\
& (-2 \cdot q + 2s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta]) / \\
& ((q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2}) + \\
& ((1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) \\
& (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta]) / \\
& (2 (q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2}) + \\
& (4.493775893684088 \cdot 10^{16} (2q - 2 \cdot s) (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q + \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta]) / \\
& ((q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2}) - \\
& (4.038804356531245 \cdot 10^{33} w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2w \sin^2[\beta])) / \\
& ((q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2}) - \\
& (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w + \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w \sin^2[\beta])) / \\
& ((q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2}) +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (1.615521742612498 \cdot 10^{34} w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta]) / \left(\sqrt{q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2} \right. \\
& \quad \left. (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + \right. \\
& \quad \quad 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + \\
& \quad \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} \right) - \\
& (15 (1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) (-2 \cdot q + 2 s) \\
& \quad w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2 w \sin[\beta]^2)) / \\
& \left(8 (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{7/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) - \\
& (1.685165960131533 \cdot 10^{17} (2 q - 2 \cdot s) (-2 \cdot q + 2 s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \\
& \quad \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2 w \sin[\beta]^2)) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{7/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) - \\
& (15 (2 q - 2 \cdot s) (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) \\
& \quad w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2 w \sin[\beta]^2)) / \\
& \left(8 (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{7/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) - \\
& (15 (2 q - 2 \cdot s) (-2 \cdot q + 2 s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w + \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w \sin[\beta]^2)) / \\
& \left(8 (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{7/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) + \\
& (3 (1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) \\
& \quad (-2 \cdot q + 2 s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta]) / \\
& \left(2 (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) + \\
& (1.3481327681052264 \cdot 10^{17} (2 q - 2 \cdot s) (-2 \cdot q + 2 s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta]) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) + \\
& (3 (2 q - 2 \cdot s) (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) \\
& \quad w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta]) /
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(2 (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) - \\
 & (2.6962655362104528 \cdot 10^{17} w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2 w \sin[\beta]^2)) / \\
 & \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) - (1.5 \cdot w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w \sin[\beta]^2)) / \\
 & \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) + \\
 & (3.5950207149472704 \cdot 10^{17} w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta]) / \\
 & \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) + \\
 & (105 (2 q - 2 \cdot s) (-2 \cdot q + 2 s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2 w \sin[\beta]^2) \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)}) / \\
 & \left(8 (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{9/2} \right) - \\
 & (15 (2 q - 2 \cdot s) (-2 \cdot q + 2 s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)}) / \\
 & \left(2 (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{7/2} \right) + (7.5 \cdot w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2 w \sin[\beta]^2) \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)}) / (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{7/2} - \\
 & (6 \cdot w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)}) / \\
 & (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2}, \{q, 0, c\}, \{s, 0, \\
 & c\}, \{w, 0, c\}, \{\beta, 0, \pi / \\
 & 2\}
 \end{aligned}$$

... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.

... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression 0. ComplexInfinity encountered.

... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.

... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression 0. ComplexInfinity encountered.

... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.

... **General:** Further output of Power::infy will be suppressed during this calculation.

... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression 0. ComplexInfinity encountered.

... **General:** Further output of Infinity::indet will be suppressed during this calculation.

In[13]= `Manipulate[SphericalPlot3D[`

$$\begin{aligned}
 & - \left((1.685165960131533 \cdot 10^{17} (1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
 & \left(\sqrt{q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \right. \\
 & \quad \left. 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left. \left(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta] \right)^{7/2} \right) - \\
& \left(3.370331920263066 \cdot 10^{16} (1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) \right. \\
& \quad \left. (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) \right. \\
& \quad \left. w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2 w \sin^2[\beta]) \right) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{5/2} \right) - \\
& \left(3.370331920263066 \cdot 10^{16} (1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) \right. \\
& \quad \left. (-2 \cdot q + 2 s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right. \\
& \quad \left. (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w \sin^2[\beta]) \right) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{5/2} \right) - \\
& \left(3 (1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) \right. \\
& \quad \left. (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right. \\
& \quad \left. (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w \sin^2[\beta]) \right) / \\
& \left(8 (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{5/2} \right) - \\
& \left(3.370331920263066 \cdot 10^{16} (2 q - 2 \cdot s) (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right. \\
& \quad \left. (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w \sin^2[\beta]) \right) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{5/2} \right) + \\
& \left(1.3481327681052264 \cdot 10^{17} (1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) \right. \\
& \quad \left. (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right) / \\
& \left(\sqrt{q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta]} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{5/2} \right) - \\
& \left(1.2116413069593733 \cdot 10^{34} w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w \sin^2[\beta]) \right) / \\
& \left(\sqrt{q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta]} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad \left. 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin^2[\beta]^{5/2} - \\
& (3.370331920263066 \cdot (1.7975103574736352 \cdot q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) \\
& \quad (-2 \cdot q + 2s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2w \sin^2[\beta])) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{5/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} \right) - \\
& (3 (1.7975103574736352 \cdot q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) \\
& \quad (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot q + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) \\
& \quad w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2w \sin^2[\beta])) / \\
& \left(8 (q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{5/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} \right) - \\
& (3.370331920263066 \cdot (2q - 2 \cdot s) (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot q + \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2w \sin^2[\beta])) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{5/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} \right) - \\
& (3 (1.7975103574736352 \cdot q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) (-2 \cdot q + 2s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \\
& \quad \sin[\beta] (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot w + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot w \sin^2[\beta])) / \\
& \left(8 (q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{5/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} \right) - \\
& (3.370331920263066 \cdot (2q - 2 \cdot s) (-2 \cdot q + 2s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \\
& \quad (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot w + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot w \sin^2[\beta])) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{5/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} \right) - \\
& (3 (2q - 2 \cdot s) (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot q + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \\
& \quad \sin[\beta] (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot w + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot w \sin^2[\beta])) / \\
& \left(8 (q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{5/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} \right) + \\
& (4.493775893684088 \cdot (1.7975103574736352 \cdot q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) \\
& \quad (-2 \cdot q + 2s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta]) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta]^{3/2} + \\
& ((1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) \\
& (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta]) / \\
& (2 (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta]^{3/2}) + \\
& (4.493775893684088 \cdot 10^{16} (2 q - 2 \cdot s) (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q + \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta]) / \\
& ((q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta]^{3/2}) - \\
& (4.038804356531245 \cdot 10^{33} w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2 w \sin^2[\beta])) / \\
& ((q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta]^{3/2}) - \\
& (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w + \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} w \sin^2[\beta])) / \\
& ((q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{3/2} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta]^{3/2}) + \\
& (1.615521742612498 \cdot 10^{34} w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta]) / \left(\sqrt{q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta]}^2 \right. \\
& \left. (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + \right. \\
& \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + \right. \\
& \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta]^{3/2}) - \right. \\
& (15 (1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s) (-2 \cdot q + 2 s) \\
& w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2 w \sin^2[\beta])) / \\
& (8 (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{7/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])}) - \\
& (1.685165960131533 \cdot 10^{17} (2 q - 2 \cdot s) (-2 \cdot q + 2 s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \\
& \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2 w \sin^2[\beta])) / \\
& ((q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{7/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])}) -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(15 (2q - 2 \cdot s) (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot q + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) \right. \\
& \quad \left. w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left(8 (q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{7/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) - \\
& \left(15 (2q - 2 \cdot s) (-2 \cdot q + 2s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot w + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 1.7975103574736352 \cdot w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left(8 (q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{7/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) + \\
& \left(3 (1.7975103574736352 \cdot q - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) \right. \\
& \quad \left. (-2 \cdot q + 2s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right) / \\
& \left(2 (q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) + \\
& \left(1.3481327681052264 \cdot (2q - 2 \cdot s) (-2 \cdot q + 2s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) + \\
& \left(3 (2q - 2 \cdot s) (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot q + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s) \right. \\
& \quad \left. w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right) / \\
& \left(2 (q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) - \\
& \left(2.6962655362104528 \cdot w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2w \sin[\beta]^2) \right) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \right. \\
& \quad \left. \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot qs + \right. \\
& \quad 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) - (1.5 \cdot w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \\
& \quad (-1.7975103574736352 \cdot w + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot w \sin[\beta]^2)) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{5/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot qs + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 - \\
& \quad \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) + \\
& \left(3.5950207149472704 \cdot w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \right) / \\
& \left((q^2 - 2 \cdot qs + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^{3/2} \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 - \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
 & 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta] \Big) + \\
 & (105 (2 q - 2 \cdot s) (-2 \cdot q + 2 s) w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] (-2 \cdot w + 2 w \sin^2[\beta]) \\
 & \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + \\
 & 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + \\
 & 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])}) / \\
 & (8 (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{9/2}) - \\
 & (15 (2 q - 2 \cdot s) (-2 \cdot q + 2 s) w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - \\
 & 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - \\
 & 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])}) / \\
 & (2 (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{7/2}) + (7.5 \cdot w^2 \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \\
 & (-2 \cdot w + 2 w \sin^2[\beta]) \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + \\
 & 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + \\
 & 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])}) / (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{7/2} - \\
 & (6 \cdot w \cos[\beta] \sin[\beta] \sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + \\
 & 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 + \\
 & 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} w^2 \sin^2[\beta])}) / \\
 & (q^2 - 2 \cdot q s + s^2 - 1 \cdot w^2 + w^2 \sin^2[\beta])^{5/2}, \{q, 0, 5\}, \{s, 0, \\
 & 5\}, \{w, 0, c\}, \{\beta, 0, \pi / \\
 & 2\}
 \end{aligned}$$

... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.

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... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression 0. ComplexInfinity encountered.

... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.

... **General:** Further output of Power::infy will be suppressed during this calculation.

... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression 0. ComplexInfinity encountered.

... **General:** Further output of Infinity::indet will be suppressed during this calculation.

In[14]:= **w := l α**